

Assessment of Basic Reading Abilities and Learning-Gap among Early Public Primary School Pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State

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Abstract

This study investigates basic reading abilities and learning gap among early public primary school pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. The study population includes head teachers, classroom teachers, parents, and early primary pupils from 36 public primary schools. Data collection involved questionnaires, standardized reading assessments, and Woodcock Johnson Tests. Mean and independent samples t-tests were used to answer the raised research question and research hypotheses. Findings reveal that pupils exhibit below-average reading proficiency, necessitating targeted interventions. Factors influencing reading skills include parental involvement, access to resources, teacher strategies, and community reading culture. Significant differences in reading abilities exist between primary grades and urban versus rural schools. While gender disparities are not significant, addressing educational inequalities remains crucial for fostering literacy development and ensuring equitable opportunities. Recommendations include implementing literacy interventions, conducting further research, prioritizing early interventions, creating inclusive learning environments, and allocating resources to rural schools.

Keyword: Basic reading abilities, Learning gap, Early primary pupils, Government schools, Ilorin Metropolis.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increasing recognition of the critical role that early literacy skills play in shaping the educational trajectory and future success of individuals. The primary objective of education at the foundational level, as articulated in the Nigerian Policy on Education, is to inculcate "permanent literacy and ability to communicate effectively" (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013, p. 7). As foundational building blocks for academic achievement, basic reading abilities acquired during the early years of schooling lay the groundwork for continued learning and cognitive development.

However, reading is a fundamental skill that forms the bedrock of learning, particularly in basic education. It is a critical determinant of a student's success or failure, as it influences performance across all subjects. Yet, the ability to read has proven to be a significant challenge for learners worldwide, including Nigeria. Hamka (2005) states that reading is a process of transmitting of information where the author is regarded as the informant and the reader, on the other hand, is the receiver. During the reading process, the reader interacts with the author directly. Reading is defined according to Kilfoil and Van Der Walt (2007) as the ability to decode words, both prints, and meaning.

For beginning readers in nursery and primary schools to meet the reading demands of their social environment, teachers must develop in them reading readiness concepts and skills such as oral language foundation, print awareness, letter recognition skills, phono-phonemic awareness skills, sight word recognition skills as well as comprehension skills. These concepts and skills serve as a gradual development from non-reading to beginning reading (Oyetunde & Mmuodumogu, 1999; Davis, 2000; Andzayi&Ikwen, 2014). One of the skills that children need to master before they can read books is the possession of a broad, general appreciation of the nature of print (Rosenberg, 2006). Children need to be exposed to forms of print in everyday life, including conventions associated with book reading.

In other words, the persistent learning gap in education, characterized by disparities in academic achievement among students, continues to be a pressing concern worldwide. Central to understanding and addressing this gap is recognizing the critical role of basic reading skills in shaping educational outcomes. As highlighted by Strickland (2010) cited by (Oyetunde, Ojo, Korb, & Babudoh, 2018), proficiency in reading not only underpins academic success but also serves as a gateway to broader intellectual development and societal participation. Furthermore, Chris-Okafor (2014) cited by (Oyetunde, et al., 2018) underscores the importance of strong reading skills for success across all academic subjects.

The significance of basic reading skills in narrowing the learning gap cannot be overstated. Research has consistently shown that students who possess strong reading abilities are better equipped to comprehend instructional materials, engage critically with content, and ultimately achieve academic success. According to the National Reading Panel (2000), proficient readers demonstrate the ability to decode text accurately, comprehend its meaning, and make connections with prior knowledge. This ability enables them to access and internalize academic content across diverse subject areas.

On the other hand, students who struggle with reading often face significant obstacles in their educational journey. Stanovich (2017) coined the term "Matthew effects in reading" to describe how initial differences in reading proficiency can lead to widening disparities in learning outcomes over time. Difficulties in decoding text and comprehending written material can impede students' ability to access academic content, leading to frustration, disengagement, and a deepening of the learning gap.

To this end, reading is an essential skill that serves as the foundation for all learning. Without strong reading abilities, learners may struggle to acquire new knowledge, which can hinder their overall academic progress (Bartilol, 2017). Consequently, this deficiency can negatively impact performance in other subjects, leading to higher dropout rates, lower academic achievement, and reduced chances of progressing to higher levels of education. These outcomes can have a detrimental effect on the economy.

On this note, Atoni (2018) conducted a study revealing that Grade 1 learners in Uasin Gishu exhibited low reading abilities. The research also highlighted that students from urban schools outperformed their rural counterparts in reading. Wong and Abdul Aziz (2019) emphasize the necessity of identifying reading skill deficiencies among public primary school students as a crucial first step in designing targeted interventions. This approach aims to address the literacy gap effectively. Building on this foundation, the present study explores the relationship between basic reading skills and the learning gap among early primary pupils in government schools within Ilorin Metropolis.

The learning gap in education persists as a significant challenge, particularly among early primary pupils in government schools located in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. Despite efforts to enhance educational outcomes, disparities in academic achievement persist, with basic reading skills playing a crucial role in shaping these discrepancies. In view of this, researchers like Strickland (2010), Chris-Okafor (2014) and National Reading Panel (2000) acknowledged the importance of basic reading skills, there remains a gap in understanding how these skills specifically contribute to learning discrepancies among early primary pupils in government schools in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

It is against this background that this study to address this gap by investigating the relationship between basic reading skills and learning discrepancies among early primary pupils in government schools located in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. By delving deeper into this relationship, the study aims to uncover the factors influencing the acquisition and development of basic reading skills among early primary pupils.

Objectives of the study

The study aimed at assessing the basic reading abilities and learning gap among early public primary school pupils in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. Specifically, the study has the following objectives.

1. To assess the current levels of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis.
2. To identify the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in the Ilorin Metropolis.
3. To ascertain the significant difference between basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level.
4. To ascertain the significant difference between basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender.
5. To ascertain the significant difference between basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis?
2. What are the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis?

Research Hypotheses

Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance ($P < .05$).

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey research design. The study population comprised head teachers, classroom teachers, parents of early primary pupils (class 1-3), and early primary school pupils. According to the Planning, Research and Statistics Department SUBEB (2024), there are 1,578 public primary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. However, the target population for this study consisted all the 211 Public Primary Schools in Ilorin Metropolis, the sample for the study comprised 385 respondents (www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator), consisting of 72 head teachers, 72 classroom teachers, 72 parents of early primary pupils (class 1-3), and 169 early primary school pupils (class 1-3). A multistage sampling procedure involving various sampling methods was adopted to select the sample for the study. The researcher selected 12 public primary schools from each stratum (from each Local Government in Ilorin Metropolis) using stratified random sampling technique, for a total of 36 public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. From each school selected, 36 head teachers and 36 classroom teachers were selected using purposive sampling technique based on their qualifications as experts in primary education, while 2 parents were selected using accidental sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 169 early primary school pupils (class 1-3).

However, three research instruments were used to collect data for this study. The first instrument was questionnaire designed by the researcher, the second instrument was Standardized Reading Assessments (SRA) covered various aspects of reading, including decoding skills, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension, while the third instrument was Woodcock Johnson Test (WJT) for measuring learning gap. The instruments were given to the experts in primary education to establish the content validity while experts in test development were consulted for construct validity. The observations and suggestions made by experts were used for the final preparation of the instruments. In computing the reliability of this research instruments, split-half method was employed to test internal consistency of the instruments, the instruments were administered to 40 stakeholders comprising 10 head teachers, 10 classroom teachers, 10 parents and pupils (class 1-3). Their responses to the items on these instruments were used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument which yielded a reliability of 0.78, 0.81 and 0.92 respectively. Descriptive and inferential analyses were employed to analyze the data collected for this study. Specifically, mean and independent samples t-tests were used to answer the raised research question and research hypotheses

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=216	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Pupil's current level of basic reading abilities (e.g., decoding skills, fluency, and comprehension) on a scale of 1 to 5 is above average.		2.06	0.74	Disagree
2.	Pupil's current level of basic reading abilities (e.g., decoding skills, fluency, and comprehension) on a scale of 1 to 5 is below average.		2.71	0.58	Agree
3.	Pupils often encounter challenges understanding what they read during classroom activities.		2.68	0.71	Agree
4.	Reading materials (e.g., books, textbooks) are available in the school library or classroom.		2.15	0.80	Disagree
5.	To a great extent pupils' home environment supports their development of reading skills.		2.28	0.86	Disagree
6.	To a great extent the pupils' socio-economic background influences their reading proficiency.		2.11	0.91	Disagree
7.	I believe the school is addressing the learning gap in basic reading abilities among early primary pupils.		2.27	0.64	Disagree
8.	Pupils often receive individualized support or intervention for improving their reading skills.		2.10	0.76	Disagree
9.	To a great extent pupil engagement in reading-related activities outside of school hours.		2.21	0.77	Disagree
10.	I am confident that pupils' basic reading abilities will improve over time with appropriate interventions and support.		2.70	0.61	Agree
	Grand Mean		2.33	0.74	Below Average

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 1 illustrates the current level of basic reading abilities and learning gap among early primary pupils (grades 1-3) in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis. Scores across all categories of primary teachers and parents fall below the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Accordingly, the grand mean of 2.33 concisely indicates that pupils in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis display a lower-than-average level of basic reading abilities compared to expected proficiency levels.

Research Question 2: What are the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=216	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Parental involvement is important in supporting their child's reading development.		2.86	0.44	Disagree
2.	I believe access to a variety of reading materials at home influences reading skills development.		2.73	0.51	Agree
3.	Teacher instruction and strategies is effect in promoting reading skills development.		2.67	0.53	Agree
4.	The availability of library resources and books are important in schools for enhancing reading skills.		2.95	0.40	Disagree
5.	I believe peer interactions and group reading activities contribute to the development of reading skills.		2.88	0.42	Disagree
6.	Digital technology (e.g., e-books, educational apps) has impact on reading skills development.		2.91	0.41	Disagree
7.	I think specialized reading programs or interventions are effective in addressing reading difficulties?		2.97	0.38	Disagree
8.	Socio-economic background has influence on reading skills development.		2.60	0.57	Disagree
9.	I believe individual differences in learning styles affect reading skills development.		2.71	0.52	Disagree
10.	A positive reading culture is important within the community		2.77	0.48	Agree

for fostering reading skills development.

Grand Mean 2.81 0.47 Above
Average

Source: Author's Computation, 2024 **Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average**

Table 2 illustrates the factors influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. Scores across all categories of primary teachers and parents surpass the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.81 succinctly indicates that, all the item statements influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis are; Parental Involvement, Access to Reading Materials at Home, Teacher Instruction and Strategies, Availability of School Library Resources, Peer Interactions and Group Reading Activities, Digital Technology, Specialized Reading Programs or Interventions, Socio-economic Background, Individual Differences in Learning Styles and Community Reading Culture.

Research Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to class level

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Primary Three	84	16.3	1.50	167	1.84	0.001	Sig.
Primary One	85	10.1	3.56				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024 Significant at $P < 0.05$.

Analysis from table 3 indicates that the computed t-value is 1.84 at a degree of freedom of 167 with a probability value of 0.001. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between primary three pupils and primary one pupils' in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to gender

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Male	84	16.3	1.50	167	2.12	0.083	Not Sig.
Female	85	16.1	1.56				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024 Significant at $P < 0.05$.

Analysis from table 4 indicates that the computed t-value is 2.12 at a degree of freedom of 167 with a probability value of 0.083. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.083 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between male and female primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location among public primary school pupils in Ilorin metropolis.

Table 5: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap with respect to school location

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Urban Schools	84	16.9	1.77	167	2.43	0.032	Sig.
Rural Schools	85	11.7	4.18				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024 Significant at $P < 0.05$.

Analysis from table 5 indicates that the computed t-value is 2.43 at a degree of freedom of 167 with a probability value of 0.032. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.032 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between pupils from urban schools and those from rural schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

The study's first finding unveiled that pupils in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis display a lower-than-average level of basic reading abilities compared to expected proficiency levels. It might be attributed to teachers' insufficient training to effectively teach reading skills. This could include a lack of understanding of the best teaching methodologies and strategies for reading instruction. This finding is supported by Lindner (2008) who reported that most pupils have low reading abilities as a result of: primary school teachers' difficulties in moving beginning readers toward immediate reading skills, pupils' lack of exposure to reading strategies and the prevailing attitude among teachers towards reading strategies. Klapwijk and Van de Walt (2011) confirmed this by stating that some primary school teachers continue to

struggle with reading instruction and remain resistant to its implementation in class. Hence, this implies that poor reading skills among pupils will hinder tertiary educational attainment and reduced employment opportunities.

The study unveiled in its second finding that indicates that all the item statements influencing the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis are; Parental Involvement, Access to Reading Materials at Home, Teacher Instruction and Strategies, Availability of School Library Resources, Peer Interactions and Group Reading Activities, Digital Technology, Specialized Reading Programs or Interventions, Socio-economic Background, Individual Differences in Learning Styles and Community Reading Culture. The presence of all these factors may signify that they may not act in isolation, but rather interact and complement each other in shaping reading skills. To concur with these findings, Lindner (2008) and Njie (2013) both believe the lack of exposure to reading strategies in class and the use of poor teaching methodologies by language teachers are some of the reasons why pupils have poor reading skills. To further corroborate with these findings, Botha et al. (2008) claim the problem of pupils' poor reading abilities is as the result of teachers not being trained to teach basic reading in class. The implication of this finding highlights the interconnectedness between various factors in fostering reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis.

The study's third discovery revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between primary three pupils and primary one pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. This finding may be attributed to developmental factors, curriculum progression, or varying levels of instructional support received by students at different grade levels. This finding corresponds with the work of Joseph (2018) who pointed out that pupils who become poor readers experience difficulties with accurately identifying and reading words at lower grades.

This implies that children who are not reading proficiently by third grade are four times more likely not to graduate from high school on time compared to proficient readers.

In the fourth finding of this study, it was revealed that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between male and female primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. This may be credited to gender-inclusive educational practices, equitable access to resources, and societal shifts towards gender equality in education. This finding corroborates with the work of Offorma (2009) who reported that there was no significant effect of gender on students' achievement in reading skills. The implication is that gender doesn't seem to affect reading ability, teachers and policymakers could focus on helping all students with their unique needs. They could create personalized learning plans or special help for students who are struggling with reading skills, regardless of their gender.

The study's fifth discovery unveiled that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of basic reading ability and learning gap between pupils from urban schools and those from rural schools in Ilorin Metropolis. Urban schools may have better-equipped facilities, more qualified teachers, and greater availability of reading materials, which can positively impact pupils' reading abilities. This finding corresponds with the assertion of Okebukola (2000) who argued that primary school pupils in urban areas are better in reading than primary school pupils in rural areas. The implication is that pupils in rural schools might not only be deprived of opportunities for personal growth and fulfillment but also undermines the overall development and prosperity of rural communities.

Conclusion

Conclusively, this research reveals significant findings regarding basic reading abilities among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis. Government school pupils demonstrate lower-than-average reading proficiency, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions. Multiple factors influence reading skills, with notable differences observed between primary grades and urban and rural school settings. While gender disparities were not significant, addressing educational inequalities is crucial for fostering literacy development and ensuring equitable opportunities for all pupils.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that;

1. Ministry of Education should implement targeted literacy interventions in government schools across Ilorin Metropolis to address the observed lower-than-average level of basic reading abilities.
2. Researchers should conduct further studies to explore the specific impact of each influencing factor identified on the acquisition and development of reading skills among primary pupils in Ilorin Metropolis.
3. Educational stakeholders, including school administrators and teachers, should prioritize early intervention strategies to address the significant difference in mean scores of basic reading ability between primary three and primary one pupils. This may involve implementing targeted reading programs and interventions tailored to the needs of each grade level to mitigate learning gaps and promote literacy development from an early age.
4. While no significant gender differences were found in reading abilities, school administrators and teachers should be trained to create inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of both male and female primary pupils.
5. Government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and community leaders should collaborate to ensure that rural schools receive adequate resources to promote literacy development and ensure equal opportunities for all pupils.

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